

An Explorative Study Of Practices At Early Childhood Care And Education Level In Azad Jammu & Kashmir, Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 15, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 17, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teachers, Private, Public, Early years, Children</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5790224</p>	<p><i>This research is being executed in Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK) to assess the practices of practitioners in the early years and identify the differences between the practices of both sectors, i.e. private and public. The study was quantitative in nature. Sampling was complete in two steps. In the first step, a stratified random sampling technique was used to identify the district from the three administrative divisions of AJK. Three districts were selected among ten based literacy rates in the Pakistan District Educational Ranking of Alif Ailaan (2017). In the second step, teachers of private and public schools from both sectors, private and public selected to collect the data. These teachers are selected through the random sampling technique. The tool for the data collection, validated by the experts and the reliability of the tool was measured from Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The results showed that principals were found to have same perceptions about teacher's practices in private and public sector schools. While, teachers responses proved that teachers in private sector using better classroom practices compared to public schools. It is encouraging to report that mean value for the social and emotional development of children found to be highest.</i></p>

Introduction

Education is one of the powerful weapons for the sustainable development of society. This was an important reason why education was mentioned at the fourth number in the world's sustainable development goals (SDGs-2015). These goals, it was stated that "To ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning". SDGs focused on Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) in its subsection 4.2 as "By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education". In Pakistan, National Education Policy (2009), for the first time in the history of policies, focused on Early Childhood Education (ECE). Unfortunately, the policy actions and goals cannot be achieved. However, policymakers and authorities know about the significance of Early Childhood Education and Care (ECCE). The latest official document, the draft of national educational policy (2017), reflected a clear priority to ECCE, so there were two major commitments in priority areas of this document, one was for holistic development of children, and the other was early childhood development (ECD) with more focus on 4-5 years old children. A proposed draft of the National Education Policy (2017) set the objective for expanding and promoting early childhood education. Lifelong learning is based upon the bringing up of the children and their early living styles.

Curriculum for Early Childhood Care and Education (2017), in line with national commitments made in national policies, focused on the holistic development of a child. In this document, holistic development refers to the emotional, physical, mental and moral growth through education. It is important to report that most of the national and provincial documents claimed that the first 1000 days of human life are the most significant to develop his skills and provide a better foundation of life. In this scenario, it is important for the early year's practitioners to practice and plan those activities which may help the children to develop these mentioned skills. Provinces in Pakistan also developed their policies of ECCE like Punjab and Sindh. As Early Childhood Educational Policy Sindh Government (2014) defined early education as the branch of education that caters to children's physical, emotional development and education from 0-8 years of age. There are different modes offered in Pakistan for early education, as some programs are part-time, part-year, while others provide full-day, full-year services. They can be publicly or privately run, non-profit, or profit, or the local school system can operate them. The mentioned modes are available and working across the country to facilitate the masses.

There have been different trends of ECCE across the globe. UNESCO (2008) reported that issues differ in developing and developed countries. In the case of the first one, an important concern was to facilitate the kids for their better growth and development. In these countries, there is also a dire need to support -families and communities- for child survival and properly brought up along with the protection, provided the proper facilities of nutrition, health and education. In the case of developed countries, most of them have focused on the quality

of Early Childhood Care and Education. For this, classroom practices, pedagogy, curriculum and professional teachers are the priorities of these systems. However, inequality is found in both kinds of countries in the form of disadvantaged groups like rural populations, low-income groups, ethnic, social groups, and those living in remote areas. However, it is worth mentioning that all policymakers agree that education should begin in the early years of life for sustainable development. In the early childhood period, children develop their fundamental values, attitudes, skills, behaviours, and habits, which may be long lasting.

Education For All (EFA) Review Report (2015) by the Ministry of Education claimed two types of Pre Primary education in Pakistan. One is called Katchi, usually in public sector schools, and the other one is quality Early Childhood Education (ECE) in the private sector. In the private sector this is named Montessori, Kindergarten and Nursery etc. This review report concluded that Katchi class has no separate classroom and trained teachers. Mostly children accompany their elder brothers/sisters and stay in the schools' premises. It was documented that there was no budget for this level, although in educational policy, all the areas were defined, and the action plan reflected that there should be a budget for the pre-primary level.

Punjab, Sindh and Federal Assembly passed some regulations for free and compulsory Early Childhood Education to all the children who are in age the group of 3-5 years. These Acts contain provisions of pre-primary and Early Childhood Education. For example, Article 9 of Right to Free and Compulsory Education Act 2012 (for ICT) passed by Senate and National Assembly, Article 9 of Sindh Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act 2013 passed by Sindh Assembly, and Article 10 of Punjab Free and Compulsory Education Act 2014 passed by Punjab Assembly made it obligatory for governments to ensure provision of free pre-primary and early childhood education for the children above the age of three years. (National Education Policy 2017).

Objectives of the study were:

- 1) To assess the practices of the teachers at Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE)
- 2) To identify the difference between the private and public sectors.

METHODOLOGY

The present study intends to assess the teachers' practices and identify the differences of teachers' practices between private and public schools at ECCE level in AJK. This research was a quantitative in nature. The scholar was motivated with the research approaches explained by [D.Stockemer et al\(2019\)](#) and [S.M.Roni et al \(2020\)](#). The survey was conducted to collect the data. As it was a first study in its nature to explore the teacher's practices at early grades. The instrument developed after comprehend overview of the available literature. The instrument designed to take the data from the teachers and principals/head teachers. This was a mixed-method research to carry out the objectives. The scholar motivated to use this method. The tool consisted of four major parts to assess the daily practices of teachers in the classrooms. Same items were in the questionnaire for the principals. The reliability of the tool measured on the Social Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Experts of the early childhood education were involve in the validation process of the tool. Pilot testing was done in other districts of AJK.

SAMPLING

Sampling has been done in two steps. In the first step, a stratified sampling technique was used. Three strata have been found in the geographical and administrative distribution of The State of Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK), which are Muzaffarabad, Poonch and Mirpur. So, one district from each division has been picked based on literacy rate. The literacy report of Alif Ailaan District Ranking 2017 was the reference of the variable. One district from the top (highest literacy rate) and one from the middle, and one from the bottom (least literacy) were selected based on their geographical location as well. Three administrative divisions have equal representation in the sample. As all of these three have one district in the selected sample as represented with red colour in the map. However, in the second step, schools have been selected based on their status, either public or private schools (Only primary Sections) from each district. This is worth mentioning that, during this step, a simple random technique is used to select the schools. The following map reflects the demographic spread of the study. Simple random technique was used to choose the teachers to be the part of the study.

Table 1: Total Primary Teachers in Sampled schools

Ser No	Public Sector(Teachers)	Private Sector (Teachers)	Total
1	160	160	320
	Public Sector (Heads, Principals, Incharge)	Private Sector (Principal, Section Head)	
2	90	90	180
Grand Total			500

State of Azad Jammu and Kashmir

Sample calculated through online calculator for sampling.

results and discussions

Both respondent principals and teachers reported, so the study can be concluded according to the objectives. Despite presenting separate tables, it was a better way to reflect the both means and frequencies in one table so the readers can get a better overview of respondents about a statement.

Difference between Responses of Private and Public Schools' Principals

Table 2: Difference between responses of Private and Public Schools' Principals

Ser No	School Type	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
1	Public	50.3444	90	4.94955
2	Private	56.9444	180	5.89444
Total		53.6444	180	5.89444

In the above table 2 (a), the difference is shown between private and public school principals' responses. The comparison was made to reflect the practices differences among both types of schools at early grades. However, either this response is significant or not, for this table, number 2 (b) is presented below.

Table 2(b): Difference between responses of Private and Public Schools' Principals

1	Difference	6.600
2	95% CI	5.1612-8.0388
3	t-statistic	9.052
4	DF	178
5	Significance level	P<0.0001

Table No.4. (b) shows that there is no significant difference between the responses of public and private school principals; the value of significance level (0.0001) is greater than that of 0.05. It reflects that school's principals in both types of schools have similar perceptions towards early education.

Relation Between Public and Private School's Practices (teachers)

Following table shows the standard deviation between two types of the schools.

Standard Deviation of public and private school's practices (teachers)

Table 3 (a)

Ser No	School Name	Mean	N	Std Dev.
1	Private	54.1625	160	6.06660
2	Public	48.0500	160	9.00021
3	Total	51.1062	320	8.25161

In table 3(a) the difference between private and public schools was measured. The comparison was made to reflect the practices differences among both types of schools at early grades.

Table : 3(b) Significance level

1	Difference	-6.421
2	95% CI	-7.8110 to -5.0314
3	t-statistic	-9.093
4	DF	295
5	Significance level	P < 0.0001

Table No. 3(b) shows that there is a significant difference between the use of AV Aids by Public and Private school teachers as the value of significance level (0.0001) is less than 0.05 if reflected on table No 4.52 (a). It can be seen that the private school teachers have extensive use of AV-Aids than public school teachers as the mean score (104.71) is greater, and the standard deviation (4.75) is less than those of public schools. In the aforementioned tables, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between the practices of the teachers at the Private and Public sectors. (Objective #02)

ASSESSMENT OF PRACTICES (Objective #01)

Scientists and early practitioners consider the four major areas of development in children. For this study, scholars add those identified and accepted areas of development in a questionnaire to explore the early year's practices of teachers. As this is the first study to explore the practices of teachers in AJK at early grades, so the basic concept is being explored to set a benchmark for the prospective researchers. The responses of the teachers/practitioners are being tabulated to understand the practices of teachers.

Physical and Motor Development

Gross Motor Development

Pushing, pulling, throwing-catching, and pedaling

Table 4: Comparison of activities to Promote Gross Motor Development

Gross Motor Development					
Item/Skill	Activity	Frequency	%age	Mean	SD
Pushing pulling, Throwing catching, Pedaling	Wheel Carts	18	5.6	1.94	0.231
	Balls	302	94.4		
Walking	No Response	135	42.2	0.58	0.495
	Circles in Grounds	185	57.8		
Kicking	Balls	97	30.3	1.70	0.460
	Games	223	69.7		

This table describes that the teachers are arranging/managing more activities (mean score value 1.94) to promote pushing-pulling, throwing-catching and pedaling, to promote the gross motor development among students. Likewise, mean score 1.70 showed that teachers are developing the skill of kicking among students, however mean score value of 0.58 is not encouraging at early grades to guide the students for proper walk.

Fine Motor Development

Table 5: Comparison of activities to promote the Fine Motor Development

Fine Motor Development					
Item/Skill	Activity	Frequency	%age	Mean	SD
Freehand drawing	Chalk on Board	87	27.2	1.73	0.446
	Pencil and Paper	233	72.8		
Paperwork (Cutting, pasting)	No Response	108	33.8	0.66	0.474
	Waste papers of different colors with scissors	212	66.3		
Constructional Play	No Response	53	16.6	0.98	0.557
	Building blocks	221	69.1		
Painting	No Response	46	14.4	1.94	0.237
	Color Wax	19	5.9		
	Water and Brushes	301	94.1		

Table 4 showed that teachers are using more activities to promote the painting skill (highest mean score 1.94) among ECCE children in Fine Motor Development. Mean score 1.73 showed that teachers are also promoting free hand drawing among children. Mean score 0.98 reflecting that teachers are trying to promote constructional play, while a minimum number of activities are being executed in ECCE classrooms to promote paper work.

SOCIAL AND EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Feelings of Belongingness

Greetings, Attend each child and addressing each child:

Table: 5: Competency of teachers to provide social Care to each child

Item	Continuous professional development	Teacher's availability	Others	Total
Greetings	285	35	0	320
Attend each child individually	201	119	0	320
Addressing each child by name	150	157	13	320
Talk to child in informal way.	90	221	9	320

Table 5 reflected that 285 teachers are professionally trained to motivate the early learners through praising their work, however only 35 teachers claimed that teachers' availability is an issue to greet the students, when they performed well. A significant number of teachers i.e. 201 claimed that they attend each child individually, however 119 claimed that due to unavailability of time, they could not attend each child. Furthermore, to promote the social and emotional attributes among the children, 150 teachers called the children with their names, while 157 claimed that they did not call the students with their real names. This reflected that there is a significant number of teachers who called the children with some nicknames or they called the children with some short names. Only 90 teachers agreed that are enough trained to have some informal talks with their students, while a large number claimed that they are busy and did not manage their availability to talk with children in informal way. Above all the activities strengthen and promote the sense of attachment and belongingness among the children to their teachers, principals, and schools. Teacher-student ratio and continuous professional development of teachers plays a vital role to manage all these activities within classroom.

Table 6: Promoting Desirable Social Behavior

Promoting desirable social Behavior					
Item/Skill	Activity	Frequency	%age	Mean	SD
Group Work, Team Work	Yes	320	100%	1.00	0.000
	Sharing-play material, food items etc	Instructions	68	15.6	0.78
Wait for their turns (encouragement)	Role Play	154	48.1		
	Demonstration	98	30.6		
	Habit formation activities	Aaya	320	100.0	1.00
Toilet Guidance		118	36.9		
Eating Habits		115	35.9		
Washing Hands (Demo)		71	22.2		
Putting back things at their respective place		320	100.0		
Birthday and other celebrations	Arrangements	16	5.0	2.94	0.921
	Cards formation	98	30.6		
	Gifts	96	30.0		
	Greetings	110	34.4		
Recognition	Clapping in the classroom	163	50.9	1.88	1.102
	Praise	84	26.3		
	Rewards	21	6.6		
	Displaying of name	52	16.3		

Table 6 showed that mean score value of 2.94 is the highest value among other activities. This leads to finding that teachers are celebrating the birthdays, and other celebrations in the ECCE classrooms or school premises, which is encouraging. Mean value, 1.88 showed that teachers recognized the ECCE students and 1.00 reflected that habit formation activities are also demonstrated/arranged at ECCE classrooms. Teachers are arranging the activities to promote the group work and team work among the student of ECCE.

Familiarizing With Immediate Physical and Social Environment

Comparison of activities to familiarize the students with immediate Physical and Social environment:

Table 7: Comparison of activities to familiarize the students with immediate Physical and Social environment

Familiarizing with Immediate Physical and Social Environment					
Item/Skill	Activity	Frequency	%age	Mean	SD
Outdoor Visits	No Response	41	12.8	1.00	0.510
	Plant collection	237	74.1		
	Social Activities	42	13.1		
Professionals of a society	No Response	41	12.8	1.03	0.533
	Meetings with Doctors or any other.	229	71.6		
	Guest Speakers	50	15.6		
Days Celebration	No Response	201	62.8	0.37	0.484
	World Days(Teachers day) etc	119	37.2		

Table 7 showed that the teachers are arranging outdoor visits to familiarize the students with their physical environment, however mean value of 0.37 is not encouraging. This is important to arrange/manage the national days/world days to promote the sense of indigenous/national culture and international trends.

Encouraging Children to be Independent

Comparison of activities to Encourage children to be Independent

Table 8: Comparison of activities to Encourage children to be Independent

Item/Skill	Activity	Frequency	%age	Mean	SD
Involvement of kids in activities and assign them roles	Teacher guidance	19	5.9	1.94	0.237
	Role plays	301	94.1		
Assign children to dress-up, comb and clean themselves	Relevant material available	70	21.9	1.78	0.414
	Demonstration	250	78.1		

Table 4.43 showed that the teachers are practicing more activities to involve the students in activities. However, mean score of 1.78 is also encouraging to reflect that teachers are also working on personality development of children to make them independent.

4.3.3 Cognitive Development

4.3.3.1 Sensory Stimulation

Table 4.49: Comparison of activities to promote the sensory Stimulation among the students

Item/Skill	Activity	Frequency	%age	Mean	SD
Sense of hearing	Games of hearing	253	79.1	1.21	0.407
	Musical instruments	67	20.9		
Sense of Touching	No Response	32	10.0	0.90	0.300
	Materials for touch	288	90.0		
Sense of Smell	No Response	127	39.7	0.60	0.490
	Objects for smell(Like Lemon, garlic, ginger etc)	193	60.3		
Sense of Taste	No Response	97	30.3	0.93	0.733
	Food stuff/articles	147	45.9		
	Games for eating competitions	76	23.8		
Aesthetic Sense	No Response	104	32.5	0.68	0.469
	State of Art school environment	216	67.5		

Table 8 showed that mean score of sense of hearing is highest as compared to other activities, which reflected that the teachers are practicing more activities to promote the sense of hearing among the students as compared to other activities.

Concept Formation

Item	Puzzles	Picture completion
Thinking, reasoning and problem solving	144	154

Table 9: Thinking, reasoning and problem solving

Above table, 9 showed that there are 144 teachers who organize different puzzles to develop thinking and reasoning skill. 154 teachers used picture completion games or activities.

Development of memory skills

Item	Text books	Activity books	Logical sequence with cards and objects	Others
Development of memory skills	122	142	19	0

Table 10: Development of memory skills

Above table, 10 showed that there were 122 teachers who used textbooks, 142 teachers who used activity books, and 19 teachers who used logical sequence with cards and objects to promote developmental memory skills.

LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT

Table 11: Comparison of activities to promote the Language Development

Item/Skill	Activity	Frequency	%age	Mean	SD
Listening	Listening games	82	25.6	1.74	0.437
	Story telling	238	74.4		
Reading	Read aloud	141	44.1	1.56	0.497
	Drilling	179	55.9		
Speaking	No Response	9	2.8	0.97	0.172
	Conversation in given situations	311	97.2		
Writing	Paper-pencil	149	46.6	2.23	1.438
	Paint and brushes	67	20.9		
	Picture books	16	5.0		
	Matching	56	17.5		
	Repetition	32	10.0		

Table 11 showed that mean score value against the activities of writing is quite high and encouraging i.e 2.23. This value leads to a finding that teachers are promoting writing skill among students, in language development, compared to other skills. Likewise, mean score for the skills of listening and reading is encouraging. However, mean score, to promote the skill of speaking is not up to the mark.

FINDINGS:

The data proved that there is no significant difference between the responses of the principals/head teachers in private and public sector. This reflected that the school leadership in both sectors i.e private and public sector, have similar perceptions about the practices of the teachers in their schools. However, teacher's responses showed that there is significant difference between the practices of the teachers. Data proved that teachers of private sector, using more AVAIDs in the classrooms (Objective #01). While assessing the practices of teachers, mean value for the skills of free handwriting (1.94), painting (1.94), recognition of children in the classrooms (1.88), listening (1.74) and involvement of children in activities and assign them roles (1.94) found higher than other required skills among the children. The highest value of mean score recorded 2.94 for the birthdays and other celebrations, and for the development of writing skill 2.23, which is encouraging. This data reflected that teachers are using such activities through which social and emotional development of children may be achieved at a maximum level. Meanwhile, language development is also more focused compared to physical and cognitive development of children. However, other areas of development like physical and cognitive development, not focused as required.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

The findings of the study lead to recommend the following important points to promote early learning:

- 1) Continuous professional development of teachers is need of hour. CPD may also helpful to overcome the issues of teacher's availability at ECCE level separately.
- 2) Training sessions and programs for Educational leadership, who are running and managing the early years learning centers.
- 3) Resource Rooms may be developed in public schools and strengthen at private schools.
- 4) A comprehensive road map to launch the ECCE classes in public schools.
- 5) Provision of separate teachers of ECCE in public schools.
- 6) Private sector may be supported to strengthen the ECCE programs.
- 7) Trained teachers in both sectors (Public and Private) may be provided through starting/launching the ECCE training programs.
- 8) Integrated ECCE programs may be launched to improve the learning of children. (Department of Health and Department of Elementary and Secondary Education)

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